

Introduction to Kalman Filtering

Paul Newman

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$$p(x_k, m|Z^{k-1}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(x_k, m|x_{k-1}, m|Z^{k-1}) dx_{k-1}$$

Why This Lecture?

- The Kalman filter is an ubiquitous estimation tool (very common in robotics)
- SLAM was first formulated using a K.F
- It lends itself to the analysis properties of the SLAM problem
- Its wholesome stuff.

Estimation is ..

“Estimation is the process by which we infer the value of a quantity of interest, \mathbf{x} , by processing data that is in some way dependent on \mathbf{x} .”

Maximum Likelihood

$$\mathcal{L} \triangleq p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) \quad p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{C} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{z}-\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{P}^{-1}(\mathbf{z}-\mathbf{x})}$$

N.B Multivariate Gaussian Understood?

Given an observation \mathbf{z} and a likelihood function $p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$, the **maximum likelihood estimator - ML** finds the value of \mathbf{x} which maximises the likelihood function $\mathcal{L} \triangleq p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{m.l} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{x}} p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

Find a value of x(state) that best explains z (data)

ML-II

ML does not incorporate prior knowledge

Maximum A Posteriori Estimation

$$\underbrace{p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})}_{\text{posterior}} = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x})}{p(\mathbf{z})}$$
$$\propto \underbrace{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})}_{\text{Likelihood}} \times \underbrace{p(\mathbf{x})}_{\text{prior}}$$

Given an observation \mathbf{z} , a likelihood function $p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$ and a prior distribution on \mathbf{x} , $p(\mathbf{x})$, the **maximum a posteriori estimator - MAP** finds the value of \mathbf{x} which maximises the posterior distribution $p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{map} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{x}} p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

MAP does incorporate prior knowledge

Example: Normal Prior and Likelihoods

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = C_1 \exp\left\{-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mu_p)^2}{2\sigma_p^2}\right\}$$

$$p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) = C_2 \exp\left\{-\frac{(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{x})^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) &= \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x})}{p(\mathbf{z})} \\ &= C(\mathbf{z}) \times p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) \times p(\mathbf{x}) \\ &= C(\mathbf{z}) \exp\left\{-\underbrace{\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mu_p)^2}{2\sigma_p^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{x})^2}{2\sigma_z^2}}_{\text{Maximise this}}\right\} \end{aligned}$$

Example Cont

$$\exp\left\{-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mu_p)^2}{2\sigma_p^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{x})^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right\}$$

Maximised when:

$$\frac{(x - \alpha)^2}{\beta^2} = -\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mu_p)^2}{2\sigma_p^2} - \frac{(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{x})^2}{2\sigma_z^2} = 0$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\sigma_z^2 \mu_p + \sigma_p^2 \mathbf{z}}{\sigma_z^2 + \sigma_p^2} \quad \beta^2 = \frac{\sigma_z^2 \sigma_p^2}{\sigma_z^2 + \sigma_p^2}$$

decreases

Mean

Variance

How does the mean change?

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{map} = \mu_p + \frac{\sigma_p^2}{\sigma_p^2 + \sigma_z^2} \times (\mathbf{z} - \mu_p)$$

Old (prior) mean

Difference between measurement and prior

Visually

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{map} = \mu_p + \frac{\sigma_p^2}{\sigma_p^2 + \sigma_z^2} \times (\mathbf{z} - \mu_p)$$

$$\sigma_{map}^2 = \frac{\sigma_z^2 \sigma_p^2}{\sigma_z^2 + \sigma_p^2}$$

Minimum Mean Squared Error Estimation

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{mmse} = \arg \min_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}} \mathcal{E} \left\{ \underbrace{(\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})^T (\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})}_{\text{Cost Function}} \mid \mathbf{Z}^k \right\}$$

Choose $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ so argument
is minimised

Expectation operator (“average”)

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is estimate \mathbf{x} is truth

Evaluating .

$$\mathcal{E}\{g(x)|y\} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|y)dx \quad \text{From probability theory}$$

$$J(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{E}\{(\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})^T(\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})|\mathbf{Z}^k\} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})^T(\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x}$$

$$\frac{\partial J(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{x})}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}} = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x} = 0$$

Splitting apart the integral, noting that $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is a constant:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\mathbf{x}}p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{x}p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x}$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{x}p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x}$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathbf{x}p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)d\mathbf{x}$$

Very Important Thing $\rightarrow \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{mmse} = \mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k\}$

Recursive Bayesian Estimation

Key idea: “one mans posterior is another’s prior” ;-)

$\mathbf{Z}^k = \{\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2 \cdots \mathbf{z}_k\}$ Sequence of data (measurements)

We want conditional mean (mmse) of \mathbf{x} given \mathbf{Z}^k

Can we iteratively calculate this – ie every time a new measurement comes in, update our estimate?

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k) = f(p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1}), p(\mathbf{z}_k|\mathbf{x}))$$

Yes

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k) = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}_k|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1})}{p(\mathbf{z}_k|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1})}$$

$$\underbrace{p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^k)}_{\text{Estimate}} \propto \underbrace{p(\mathbf{z}_k|\mathbf{x})}_{\text{Likelihood}} \underbrace{p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1})}_{\text{Last Estimate}}$$

At time k

Explains data at time k
as function of x at time k

At time k-1

Kalman Filtering

- Ubiquitous estimation tool
- Simple to implement
- Closely related to Bayes estimation and MMSE
- Immensely Popular in robotics
 - Real time
 - Recursive (can add data sequentially)

It is not that complicated!

Overall Goal

To come up with a recursive algorithm that produces an estimate of state by processing data from a set of explainable measurements and incorporating some kind of plant model

True underlying state \mathbf{x}

Part 1 – Data Fusion

True state (never known)

$$p(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} |\mathbf{R}|^{1/2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{w}\right\}$$

$$\mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{w}(i)\mathbf{w}(j)^T\} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R} & i = j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbf{z}(k) = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{w}(k)$$

Noise vector – **zero mean**

Model – explains data
in terms of state. A matrix

Data/measurement/observation from sensor
described by H. Generally a vector

k is time index

Likelihood

If Gaussian noise process \mathbf{w} has zero mean and Covariance \mathbf{R}

$$\mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{z}(k)\} = \mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{w}(k)\} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}$$

Likelihood can be written as

$$p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{nz/2} |\mathbf{R}|^{1/2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})\right\}$$

Assume we have a prior belief .

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{nx/2} |\mathbf{P}_\ominus|^{1/2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\ominus)^T \mathbf{P}_\ominus^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_\ominus)\right\}$$

Prior Covariance

Prior mean

Covariance is ..

Multi-dimensional analogy of variance

P is a symmetric matrix that describes a 1-standard deviation contour (ellipsoid in 3D+) of the pdf

Getting The Posterior

Now we can use Bayes rule to figure out an expression for the posterior $p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})$:

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}) &= \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x})}{p(\mathbf{z})} \\ &= \frac{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x}} \\ &= \frac{\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{nz/2}|\mathbf{R}|^{1/2}} \exp\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})\}}{\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{z})} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{nx/2}|\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}|^{1/2}} \exp\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus})^T \mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus})\}} \\ &\propto \exp\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})\} \exp\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus})^T \mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus})\} \\ &= \exp\{-1/2 \underbrace{((\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}) + (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus})^T \mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\ominus}))}_{\text{express as } (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\oplus})^T \mathbf{P}_{\oplus}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\oplus})}\} \end{aligned}$$

Which leads to

Comparing terms allows the following to be derived:

Updated covariance $\longrightarrow \mathbf{P}_{\oplus} = (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1}$

Updated mean $\longrightarrow \mathbf{x}_{\oplus} = (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1} (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_{\ominus} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{z})$.

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{nx/2} |\mathbf{P}_{\oplus}|^{1/2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\oplus})^T \mathbf{P}_{\oplus}^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\oplus})\right\}$$

$$\mathcal{E}\{p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})\} = \mathbf{x}_{\oplus} = \text{MMSE estimate}$$

Quick Review

1. Derived a closed form solution for MAP estimator with Gaussian sensor noise model and Gaussian Prior
2. Mean of $p(x|z)$ shown to be MMSE estimator
3. Kalman filter simply takes in observations (z) and old estimates $p(x|z)_{old}$ and produces a new estimated distribution $p(x|z)_{new}$
4. If pdfs are Gaussian we only need talk about mean and Covariance and from (2) the mean is the best estimate

Inverting the Inverse

$$\mathbf{P}_{\oplus} = (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\oplus} = (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1} (\mathbf{P}_{\ominus}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_{\ominus} + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{z}).$$

Can be re-written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{\oplus} &= \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} - \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \mathbf{H}^T (\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \mathbf{H}^T)^{-1} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \\ &= \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{W}^T \\ &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H}) \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S} &= \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R} \\ \mathbf{W} &= \mathbf{P}_{\ominus} \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{S}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Covariance decreases
when sensor data is
fused with prior

And a new state update Eqn:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\oplus} = \mathbf{x}_{\ominus} + \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_{\ominus})$$

New estimate
(mean of pdf)

Real observation

Best previous
estimate

Predicted observation

Kalman Update Equations:

Given an observation \mathbf{z} with uncertainty (covariance) \mathbf{R} and a prior estimate \mathbf{x}_\ominus with covariance \mathbf{P}_\ominus the new estimate and covariance are calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x}_\oplus &= \mathbf{x}_\ominus + \mathbf{W}\nu \\ \mathbf{P}_\oplus &= \mathbf{P}_\ominus - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{W}^T\end{aligned}$$

where the “**Innovation**” ν is

$$\nu = \mathbf{z} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_\ominus$$

the “**Innovation Covariance**” \mathbf{S} is given by

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_\ominus\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}$$

and the “**Kalman Gain**” \mathbf{W} is given by

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{P}_\ominus\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{S}^{-1}$$

We can use the “recursive Bayesian” result to allow us to use one iteration’s estimate (posterior) as the next iteration’s prior

The $i|j$ notation

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(i|j)$ is the estimate of \mathbf{x} at time i given measurements up until time j . Commonly you will see the following combinations:

- $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k)$ estimate at time k given all available measurements. Often simply called the **estimate**
- $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k - 1)$ estimate at time k given first $k - 1$ measurements. This is often called the **prediction**

$$\mathbf{P}(i|j) = \mathcal{E}\left\{ \underbrace{(\mathbf{x}(i) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(i|j))}_{\text{true}} \underbrace{(\mathbf{x}(i) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(i|j))}_{\text{estimated}}^T \mid \underbrace{\mathbf{Z}^j}_{\text{Data up to } t=j} \right\}$$

This is useful for derivations but we can never use it in a calc as \mathbf{x} is unknown truth!

Incorporating Plant Models

We have modelled the noisy sensor as a $z(k) = Hx(k) + w(k)$

We may also have a (noisy) understanding of how the state evolves with time and other control inputs

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(k-1) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{v}(k)$$

The diagram shows the state equation $\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(k-1) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{v}(k)$ with four arrows pointing from labels below to terms in the equation: 'new state' points to $\mathbf{x}(k)$, 'Previous state' points to $\mathbf{x}(k-1)$, 'control' points to $\mathbf{u}(k)$, and 'noise' points to $\mathbf{v}(k)$.

Note this is a truth model not an estimation equation – no $i|j$

Predicting the mean:

From the “MMSE” result

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) &= \mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{x}(k|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1})\} \\ &= \mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(k-1) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{v}(k)|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1}\} \\ &= \mathbf{F}\mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{x}(k-1)|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1}\} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{G}\mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{v}(k)|\mathbf{Z}^{k-1}\} \\ &= \mathbf{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{0}\end{aligned}$$

Last best estimate

Control at time k e.g. steering

Noise term is unknown
but zero mean doesn't
affect prediction

Predicting the Covariance

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) = \mathcal{E}\{(\mathbf{x}(k) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1))(\mathbf{x}(k) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1))^T | \mathbf{Z}^{k-1}\}$$

Substitution and cancellation (zero mean) gives

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}(k-1|k-1)\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{G}^T$$

This result should also seem familiar to you - remember that if $\mathbf{x} \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{P})$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}$ then $\mathbf{y} \sim N(\mathbf{F}\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{F}^T)$?.

Q is the strength of the process noise, \mathbf{v} , - its covariance

Prediction + Update:

Rewriting update equations using $k|k$ notation:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) + \mathbf{W}(k)\nu(k)$$

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k) = \mathbf{P}(k|k-1) - \mathbf{W}(k)\mathbf{S}\mathbf{W}(k)^T$$

$$\nu(k) = \mathbf{z}(k) - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}(k|k-1)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}(k|k-1)\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}$$

$$\mathbf{W}(k) = \mathbf{P}(k|k-1)\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{S}^{-1}$$

Combining with Prediction

Linear Kalman Filter Equations

prediction:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) = \mathbf{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(k) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}(k-1|k-1)\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{G}\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{G}^T \quad (2)$$

update:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) + \mathbf{W}(k)\nu(k) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{P}(k|k) = \mathbf{P}(k|k-1) - \mathbf{W}(k)\mathbf{S}\mathbf{W}(k)^T \quad (4)$$

where

$$\nu(k) = \mathbf{z}(k) - \mathbf{H}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}(k|k-1)\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{W}(k) = \mathbf{P}(k|k-1)\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{S}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Crucial Characteristics

- Asynchronicity
- Prediction Covariance Inflation
- Update Covariance Deflation
- Observability
- Correlations

Example - Landing on Mars

[A fine Movie](#)

Mars Lander Example

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} h \\ \dot{h} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{state}$$

$$\mathbf{z}(k) = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{w}(k) \quad \text{obs model}$$

$$\mathbf{z}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{c} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} h \\ \dot{h} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{w}(k)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \delta T \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}} \mathbf{x}(k-1) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\delta T^2}{2} \\ \delta T \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{G}} \mathbf{v}(k) \quad \text{plant model}$$

Trajectory

Innovation

$$\nu(k) = \mathbf{z}(k) - \mathbf{H}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1)$$

Non-Linear Kalman Filtering

Same trick as in Non-linear Least Squares:

- Linearise around a current estimate using jacobian
- Problem becomes linear again

Complete derivation is in the notes but

To convert the linear Kalman Filter to the Extended Kalman Filter simply replace \mathbf{F} with $\nabla\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathbf{H} with $\nabla\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}}$ **in the covariance and gain calculations only**. The jacobians are always evaluated at the best available estimate ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1)$ for $\nabla\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1)$ for $\nabla\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}}$

Prediction:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underbrace{\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1)}_{\text{predicted state}} &= \overbrace{\mathbf{f}(\underbrace{\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k-1|k-1)}_{\text{old state est}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{u}(k)}_{\text{control}}, k)}^{\text{plant model}} \\
 \underbrace{\mathbf{P}(k|k-1)}_{\text{predicted covariance}} &= \nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}} \underbrace{\mathbf{P}(k-1|k-1)}_{\text{old est covariance}} \nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}}^T + \underbrace{\nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{v}} \mathbf{Q} \nabla \mathbf{G}_{\mathbf{v}}^T}_{\text{process noise}} \\
 \underbrace{\mathbf{z}(k|k-1)}_{\text{predicted obs}} &= \overbrace{\mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1))}^{\text{observation model}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Update:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underbrace{\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k)}_{\text{new state estimate}} &= \overbrace{\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) + \mathbf{W} \underbrace{\nu(k)}_{\text{innovation}}}_{\text{prediction and correction}} \\
 \underbrace{\mathbf{P}(k|k)}_{\text{new covariance estimate}} &= \underbrace{\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{W}^T}_{\text{update decreases uncertainty}} \nu(k) = \underbrace{\mathbf{z}(k)}_{\text{measurement}} - \mathbf{z}(k|k-1) \\
 \mathbf{W} &= \underbrace{\mathbf{P}(k|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}}^T \mathbf{S}^{-1}}_{\text{kalman gain}} \\
 \mathbf{S} &= \underbrace{\nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{P}(k|k-1) \nabla \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{x}}^T}_{\text{Innovation Covariance}} + \mathbf{R}
 \end{aligned}$$

Recalculate Jacs at each iteration

Lets be Clear about Jacobians..

Consider a function \mathbf{f} which maps a vector \mathbf{x} ($m \times 1$) to a vector \mathbf{y} ($n \times 1$). We also allow the transformation to be a function of another vector \mathbf{u} .

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$$

Lets think of this as a stacked vector of functions (one for each element of \mathbf{y}) and lets write out \mathbf{x} element by element:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(\overbrace{x_1, \dots, x_m}^{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{u}) \\ \vdots \\ f_n(x_1, \dots, x_m, \mathbf{u}) \end{bmatrix}$$

The term $\nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}}$ is understood to be the jacobian of (\mathbf{f}) with respect to \mathbf{x} evaluated at a specified value of \mathbf{x} :

$$\nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_1}{\partial x_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_1}{\partial x_m} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_n}{\partial x_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_n}{\partial x_m} \end{bmatrix}$$

This is a matrix of functions.
We'll always be told what value of \mathbf{x} to use to turn it into a matrix of numbers.

Had we be talking about $\nabla \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{u}}$ then we would have differentiated w.r.t \mathbf{u} and ended up with a $n \times \dim(\mathbf{u})$ matrix

And now the fun part

Using a EKF to do some robotics .

But you'll have to wait until the next lecture